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Forest Regulation and Forest Conservation Practice Among Farmers in Boki Local Government Area, Cross River State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The main purpose of this study was to investigate forest regulation and forest conservation practice among farmers in Boki Local Government Area, Cross River State, Nigeria. To give direction to this study, two research questions and null hypotheses respectively guided the study. The review of related literature was carried out base on specific objectives of the study. Survey research design was adopted for the study. The targeted population was all the farmers in Boki Local Government Area, Cross River State in 2023 farming season. Multi-stage sampling techniques was adopted in selecting six hundred and sixty-seven (667) respondents used for the study. twenty (20) items four-point scale questionnaire titled “education for forest regulation and forest conservation Questionnaire” (FRFCQ) was used for data collection. To test the hypotheses formulated for the study, simple linear regression statistical tool was used for data analysis. The hypotheses formulated was tested at .05 level of significance. The result of the finding revealed that forest regulation significantly influences forest conservation in Boki Local Government Area in Cross River State. Based on the findings it was recommended that forest regulation should be expanded and intensified in Boki Local Government Area in Cross River State.

Keywords: sustainable, forest management practices, forest conservation, farmers, Boki Local Government Area

Introduction

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Ministry of Lands and Environment noted that forest ecological system effect or degradation is created by the consolidation of an effectively substantial and expanding human populace, constantly expanding monetary development or per capita fortune and the application of asset exhausting and polluting technology. It occurs when forest natural resources are depleted and the forest environment is compromised in the form of extinction or drastic reduction of forest species, pollution in air, water and soil, and rapid growth in population of unwanted forests species (Ministry of Lands and Environment, 2022). Forest degradation is one of the largest threats that are being faced by Cross River State and Boki Local Government Area today. The United Nations International Strategy for Disaster Reduction characterizes forest degradation as the lessening of the limit of the earth to meet social and forest destinations, and needs. Forest degradation can happen in a number of ways. At the point when forests environments are wrecked or common assets are exhausted, the forest environment is considered to be corrupted and harmed (FAO, 2020). Forest issues can be seen by long term ecological effects, some of which can demolish whole environments (climate change). A forest is a unique unit and incorporates all the living and non-living components that live inside it. Plants and creatures are evident parts of the forest environment, but it also includes the things on which they depend on, for example, streams, lakes, and soils. The forest is to be protected without compromise from all stakeholders. Despite the sustainable forests management practices in place; in 2019 Cross River State had the highest rate of deforestation in the world, according to the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO, 2020). In 2005 12.2%, the equivalent of 11,089,000 hectares had been deforested in Nigeria. Between 2000 and 2020, Nigeria lost an average of 409,700 hectares of forest every year equal to an average annual deforestation rate of 2.38%. Between 2005 and 2019, in total Nigeria lost 35.7% of its forest cover, or around 6,145,000 hectares (FAO, 2020).

Forest ecosystems are important habitats for a vast number of species worldwide. These ecosystems are degrading faster than they are regenerating, due to the increased demand for natural resources and the continued application of non-sustainable practices by humans. In order to protect these important ecosystems, the designation of protected areas (PAs) has become the primary policy tool for forest conservation and the provision of ecosystem services nowadays. According to the International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN) approximately 10% of forests across the world are officially designated as protected areas (Dudley & Phillips, 2006). Presently, the country has different policies within sub-sectors of agriculture and the forest involved in land use. There is need for integrated planning and management of all our rural development programmes. This will reduce conflicts and guarantee better resources use. With the assistance of some international organizations including the FAO, World Bank, UNDP, ADB, DFID (ODA), Ford Foundation, etc. strategies have been formulated and developed for effective sustainable management of a number of forest reserves in the country (FAO & UNDP, 2021). Gizachew, Rizzi, Shirima and Zahabu (2020) found that most PAs were effective in reducing deforestation rates, even if there were important pressures in their surrounding lands. BujoczekZieba and Bujoczek (2000) found that the quality of forest habitats under strict and active protected status in the regions was enhanced relative to that of managed forests. Maruna, Crnčević and Milojević (2019) describe the historical context of forest planning and management processes and discuss how the concept of land use planning for urban forest protection was established in the country through the critical re-assessment of the institutional structure of land use planning in a post-socialist environment. In the Western Terai Region of Nepal, timber harvesting increased substantially three years after scientific forest management implementation in community forestry systems, even if mean timber volume was reduced for community forest users Maruna, Crnčević and Milojević (2019).

Despite the increase in policy initiatives such as those mentioned above, meeting biodiversity conservation targets remains problematic, as many areas face continuous pressures. In the study by Wade, Austin, Cajka, Lapidus, Everett, Galperin, Maynard and Sobel (2020) the authors estimated global trends in tree cover loss between 2001 and 2018. They found a remarkable loss of forested land inside PAs, and a similar pattern in temporal trends in forest loss in PAs compared to those of global forest loss. These challenges are expected to be further aggravated by the COVID-19 pandemic. The actual long-term impacts of the pandemic on environmental and socio-economic issues are expected to be extremely complex and will take several years to be thoroughly explored. A collaborative study by researchers and practitioners from European PAs is presented McGinlay, Gkoumas, Holtvoeth, Fuertes, Bazhenova, Benzoni, Botsch, Martel, Sánchez and Cervera (2020), with some initial findings on how COVID-19 has caused an increase in PA visitors, accompanied by an increase in irresponsible behaviours bringing additional challenges for management authorities. Laktić, Žiberna, Kogovšek, Pezdevšek and Malovrh (2020) analyze links and relations between different stakeholders during participatory planning processes of the Natura 2000 management program in Slovenia. A main direction proposed by the authors is that groups of stakeholders from different institutions and sectors must be further empowered in order to be included in such processes. Similar issues emerged in the study by Kimengsi, Bhusal, Aryal, Fernandez, M.V.B.C. Owusu, Chaudhary and Nielsen (2019) in Nepal; the authors highlighted the need to include underprivileged groups in co-management processes in the Annapurna Conservation Area who

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remain highly motivated to participate despite the current top-down approach. Furthermore, in the study by Pezdevšek Malovrh, Paletto, Posavec, Dobšinska, Dordević, Marić, Avdibegović, Kitchoukov, Stijović and Trajkov (2019); the authors identify a lack of stakeholder engagement and participation as one of the main parameters negatively influencing the implementation of conservation policies in several EU and non-EU countries. In close relation to engagement and empowerment, trust in specific entities and organizations is another important factor that needs to be taken into consideration.

In the study by Referowska and Chodak (2020); the authors found that levels of trust towards foresters were high, leading to a favourable opinion for this specific group to have a more leading role in nature conservation policies. Forests provide a variety of goods to local communities such as timber, food, fuel, and pharmaceutical products. Nevertheless, the equitable distribution of benefits derived from forests among users remains unclear. In a study conducted in the Western Terai Region of Nepal, most of produced timber was distributed among middle- and high-class groups, while poor households had very limited access to these resources Bhusal, Karki and Kimengsi (2020). In Mount Cameroon National Park, near the Kayang forest, Akonwi and Majory (2020) found through an ethnographic study, that state regulations restricted to some extent access to natural resources for local communities. However, the authors identified alternative unofficial pathways, which allowed customary practices to take place, and access to resources was possible for local communities via informal processes. Common management activities aimed at reducing high deforestation rates in large PAs and connecting these areas through restored forest corridors at the landscape level were proposed as a main priority in the study by Gizachew, Rizzi, Shirima and Zahabu (2020) in connectivity of forests with corridors was also proposed to promote long-term persistence of sacred church forests in northern Ethiopia by increasing species dispersal rates and reducing human disturbance within forests Woods, Bitew Mekonnen, Baez-Schon, Thomas, Scull, Abraha Tsegay and Cardelús, (2020). Restoration of the structure and composition of remaining forest habitats and afforestation were proposed to be adopted in the Mississippi Alluvial Valley, as a small percentage of the forest patch area was currently protected (Elliott, Mini, McKnight and Twedt, 2020).

Following a more holistic approach, Ola and Benjamin [22] demonstrated in Western Africa, that both environmental protection and economic goals must be combined before effective environmental protection can take place. However, poverty alleviation targets must not be completely ignored, as many West Africans rely on forest and catchment resources to support their livelihoods (Ola and Benjamin, 2019). Federal Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development (FMARD, 2010), is in charge of articulating Agricultural Land Use and Practices Policy for the country. There is no Land Use Policy in the country. There is however, a Land Use Act. States are being encouraged to derive their legislation from the national framework. A national forest and wildlife law is being developed with the involvement of all stakeholders. There is no forest certification practice in the country. However, public involvement on forest certification is being articulated in the proposed revised policy which will encourage private sector and NGO participation. It is being proposed that a National Working Group (NWG) on Sustainable Forest Management (SFM) and certification be set up to finalize the criteria or indicators for Sustainable Forest Management in the country. The following activities promote the use of forest products in place of products made of non-renewable materials: low tariff on wood products, reasonable pricing of wood products, under valuation of forest products, high cost of non-renewable materials especially energy and value system and traditional beliefs - preference in taste for food/delicacy prepared with fuelwood (Ola and Benjamin, 2019).

Nigeria started implementing the National Forestry Action Plan (NFAP) in 1990 with the assistance of FAO and a grant of US \$690,000 from UNDP. In order to ensure the greatest commitment at the highest and at all levels of Government, the National Advisory Council, assisted by a National Technical Committee, was inaugurated in 1994. The project was concluded in 1995 and the final NFAP report has been submitted. The next stage is to use the report to canvass for international funding from donors to implement the action plans (FAO, 2020). From literature reviewed, forest degradation has different and diverse influence on agricultural productivity. For instance, high intensity of heat resulted to discomfort for both the farmer and farm resources. Few related studies on aware creation and forest conservation have been conducted in other parts of the world and they varied in their methodology. To the best of the researcher's knowledge, none of such studies focused on forest regulation and awareness creation were conducted in Nigeria or Cross River State. This study was therefore meant to fill the gap.

Climate change has increased the region temperature, reduced the air quality we breath, pollute water, caused flooding, changes in seasons, infrastructural decay; increased pests and diseases, reduced soil fertility and reduced crops yields over the years and farmers are blaming the supreme being for the changes in climate and seasons while they keep on exploring and exploiting the earth's resources. Unless climate change is tackled, all the "best efforts" to help this great country, to come out of food shortages could be to no avail. One of the biggest threats is growing climate unpredictability, which makes subsistence farming difficult. This study posed the following questions: are farmers aware that the earth's temperature is rising because of

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some of their farming activities?, are awareness strategies or sources of information that farmers in Boki Local Government Area obtain information are assessable to farmers?, are the farmers' in Boki Local Government Area applying the forest regulation, awareness creation to aid forest conservation?, does the sustainable forest regulation applied by government improve farm productivity and environmental safety?

Objective of the Study

The main objective of the study is to investigate forest regulation and forest conservation practice among farmers in Boki Local Government Area, Cross River State, Nigeria.

Research Question

The following research questions was raised to guide the study:

To what extent does forest regulation influence farmers' forest conservation practice?

Hypothesis

The following hypothesis was formulated to guide the study:

Forest regulation has no significant influence on farmers' forest conservation practice.

Methodology

The research deign adopted for this study is the descriptive survey research design. Ndiyo (2005) defined survey research as a scientific experiment conducted on a large scale on a defined population to determine some desirable characteristic of a population. Survey research is research that is directed towards determining the nature of the situation that exits at the time of investigation. He describes that it is a type of research that studies large and small population by selecting and studying sample chosen from the population to discuss the relative incidence distribution, interrelation of sociological variables.

Survey research deigns is therefore useful for opinion and attitude studies. The research area for this study was the entire Boki Local Government Area of Cross River State. Boki Local Government Area on the north is bounded with Boki Local Government Area, on the South with Etung Local Government Area, on the East by Ikom/Ogoja Local Government Area. The local government lies between longitude 8°22'E and 9°12'E of the Greenwich meridian and latitudes 5°5'N to 6°15'W of the equator. The local government area is known for promotion of cultural festival and tourist attraction that sustains the local government policy for peaceful co-existence among members of the society, talents discovery and arts exhibition.

Educationally, primary, post primary schools abounds in Boki Local Government Area. Boki Local Government Area land and forest are fertile for the cultivation of crops such as yams, cassava, groundnut, palm oil and palm wine. Travelling across the local government area, most communities display the stereotype of crops produced as a heritage that must be presented which encourages individuals to be productive citizens. The population of the study comprises all the farmers in Boki Local Government Area, Cross River State. There are sixteen thousand, seven hundred and thirty (16730) registered farmers in Boki Local Government Area, Cross River State during the 2022/2023 farming season. Female farmers dominate the population in the research area with 9030 while the males are 7700. The researchers adopted multi-stage sampling techniques to select the sample for this study. Simple random sampling again will be used to select wards used while accidental sampling technique will be used to administer the instruments to the number of subjects used as sample. To do this, names of Wards in Boki Local Government (stratum) will be written each in piece of paper, folded and put in a container and properly shuffle together. Those that picked yes will be used as respondents in the study while those that picked no will be dropped.

The sample size for this study was 667 male and female farmers from six (6) wards in Boki Local Government, Cross River State during the 2022/2023 farming season. The number of farmers selected was to obtain adequate representative samples of farmers from the Local Government Areas. All the selected wards in the LGA were used to ensure equal representation in the study. Out of the respondents selected for the study, 343 are female while 324 are male respectively. The instruments used for data collection was a set of survey questionnaire called "Forest Regulation and Forest Conservation Practice (FRFCPQ)". The questionnaire was divided into three sections A, B and C. Section A focused on the personal data of the farmers such as sex, age, local government area of farmer, educational qualification. Section B elicited information on the various climate change awareness strategies under studies while section C measure mitigation measures among farmers. To ensure the extent to which the instrument measured what it purports to measure, the Forest Regulation and Forest Conservation Practice (FRFCPQ) was developed by the researcher through extensive literature review. The instrument was first given to two lecturers in the department of Social Science Education to scrutinize for item relevance to the variables under consideration. While some items were merged few others were re-written for inclusion in the instrument as a result of the scrutiny. The instrument was validated by two experts in measurement and evaluation and finally it was examined by the project supervisor.

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The instrument was giving to experts in measurement and evaluation for validation. Finally, the supervisor certified the face and content validities of the instrument, coverage, appropriateness and consistency with the blue print of the instrument will be certified by the supervisor.

To ascertain the reliability of the instrument, a trial test was conducted in Akankpa LGA on 50 farmers drawn from the population who are not members of the sample to be used for the study. The single test reliability method was adopted. In this approach, the instrument was administered to the sample. The responses from the administration were correlated using Crombach alpha Coefficient statistic. The Cronbach alpha coefficient results showed a reliability coefficient ranging from 0.676 to 0.732 which indicated that the instrument was reliable enough to be used for this study. The researcher with the help of research assistant carryout the administration of the questionnaire in all the wards that were selected to participate in the study. There was prior notice given to all the heads of the villages selected notifying them about the researcher's intention to visit their village. The instrument was administered on the sample group under the closed supervision of the researcher and research assistants. The research assistants were trained of the techniques involved in the administration of the instruments. There are therefore asked to ensure individual farmers' concentration and also prevent exchange of information and discussion of any form among the subjects. Six hundred and sixty-seven (667) copies of questionnaire were administered, but six hundred and fifty-two (652) were properly filled and returned. The researcher developed a key, which served as a guide for coding the data collected for, analysis. The items on the questionnaire were sorted based on the variables measured. The total number of the responses ticked (✓) in each of the section covering all the variables under the study was added. The total scores for each section were recorded against these variables. Linear regression statistical technique will be use in the analysis. These scores will be recorded on the blank column as indicated by the researcher.

Results

Hypothesis 1

Forest regulation has no significant influence on farmers' forest conservation practice.

Table 1: Simple linear regression analysis of forest regulation and forest conservation practice among farmers (N = 652)

Model	R	R ²	Adj.R ²	Std error of estimate	
1	.180	.033	.031	4.16558	
Source of variance	SS	Df	MS	F	Sig
Regression	379.446	1	379.446	21.869	.000
Residual	11278.830	650	17.352		
Total	11658.276	651			

$p < .05$, $F = 21.869$; $df = 1, 650$,

The independent variable in this hypothesis is forest regulation while the dependent variable is forest conservation among farmers. Simple linear regression statistical tool was used for data analysis because both independent and dependent variables are measured continuously. The result of this analysis is presented in Table 1. The result of analysis presented in Table 1 showed that the predictor or independent variable (forest regulation) significantly influence the predicted variable (forest conservation among farmers). The predictor variable accounted for only 3.3% of the variance in forest conservation among farmers in Boki Local Government Area, Cross River State. This showed a very weak relationship between the predictor and predicted variables. Furthermore, the regression ANOVA revealed there was a moderate significant positive influence of forest regulation on forest conservation among farmers $F(1, 650) = 21.869$; $p < .05$. Based on this result, it was revealed that the more the forest regulation provided for local farmers, the better the conservation practices they would adopt to cope with the harsh effects of climate change in the localities. Again, if the forest regulation decline, the conservation practices adopted by farmers will also decline in the area of this study.

Discussion of findings

This section focuses on the discussion of the findings obtained in the study based on each hypotheses formulated to guide the study. The finding from analysis and testing of hypothesis one showed that the null hypothesis was upheld. This implied that forest regulation significantly influences forest conservation practice among farmers in Boki Local Government Area, Cross River State. This could be based on the assumption that there are very low forest regulations provided in the study

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area or that most forest regulation do not cover forest conservation practices among farmers in the study area. It is predicted that if the level of forest regulation increase, farmers will increasingly adopt positive conservation practices that would enable them cope with the effects associated with changes in climate. The finding of this study is in line with the finding of Dudley and Phillips (2006) which revealed that in order to protect these important ecosystems, the designation of protected areas (PAs) has become the primary policy tool for forest conservation and the provision of ecosystem services nowadays. According to the International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN) in Dudley and Phillips (2006) approximately 10% of forests across the world are officially designated as protected areas.

Conclusion

Forest management practices have become increasingly obvious especially in the area of this study. The need for people especially the rural inhabitants to develop forest conservation practices has become paramount in order to cushion the harsh effects associated with such changes. Environmental awareness has been identified as a viable tool that can be utilized to sensitize and build capacity for forest management. It has therefore become an issue of utmost consideration among various stakeholders to brace up and empower the vulnerable with requisite support that would enable them cope with the effects experienced as a result of climate change. This is because an uninformed or poorly informed individual lives in uncertainty and cannot save the environment from further degradation and damage. Hence, the need to raise a citizenry that is aware of and capable of participating actively in solving environmental problem and preventing the occurrence of new ones at all times.

Recommendations

Based on the findings obtained in this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Forest regulation should be expanded and intensified in the study area in order to enable farmers developed better and improved forest conservation.
2. Awareness creation should be used more effectively in sensitizing and building the capacity of farmers to be able to cope with and adopt positive and forest conservation among farmers.

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